

Why the Ultra-Rich Pay Less Tax Than You

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“Capital income is becoming tax free.”

Emmanuel Saez and Gabriel Zucman make a bold claim in their new book, *The Triumph of Tax Injustice: How the Rich Dodge Taxes and How to Make Them Pay*. According to these leading economists on corporate tax avoidance, capital income is on the path to becoming tax-free.

Far from remaining in the academic ivory tower, Saez and Zucman have actively shaped public debate—most notably by designing Elizabeth Warren’s proposed wealth tax during the U.S. presidential campaign.

The “Smart” Way to Avoid Taxes

They open their book with a striking observation from the 2016 U.S. presidential campaign. On live television, Hillary Clinton challenged Donald Trump on his tax affairs. Trump didn’t deny dodging taxes. Instead, he proudly declared that avoiding taxes “makes him smart” and pointed out that many of Clinton’s donors did the same. The implication? Rich people are smart, and that’s why they avoid taxes. It’s also why they stay rich.

This idea—that tax avoidance is a mark of intelligence—is rarely spoken but widely accepted. An entire industry exists to make it possible. Ireland, for instance, has built a world-class reputation in providing legal and accounting services that help multinational corporations and wealthy individuals minimize tax obligations. The professionals behind these schemes are often credited with fueling Ireland’s economic rise from rags to riches.

But let’s be clear: helping multinationals dodge corporate tax is a massive financial gift to the richest of the rich. Lower corporate taxes mean higher profits, which are funneled to shareholders—who are overwhelmingly wealthy individuals. Yet, the deeper issue remains unspoken: this practice erodes democracy.

The Illusion of Trickle-Down Economics

The justification for low taxes on capital is the familiar argument that capitalism harnesses human greed for the common good. Less taxation, the theory goes, leads to more investment and job creation—a central tenet of trickle-down economics. However, today, even mainstream economists dismiss trickle-down as a failed idea.

Instead of broad economic benefits, tax avoidance has fueled skyrocketing wealth inequality. The share of total U.S. income going to the top 1% has doubled from 10% to 20% in just two decades, while their tax contributions have plummeted. In 1970, America's richest paid over 50% of their income in taxes. Today, they pay closer to 20%. Even more shocking, the 400 richest billionaires now pay a lower tax rate than the bottom 50% of Americans. In other words, multi-billionaires contribute less in taxes than someone earning just \$18,500 per year. This, according to Saez and Zucman, is the ultimate triumph of tax injustice.

A Regressive Tax System

Contrary to popular belief, the U.S. no longer has a progressive tax system. Instead, it has effectively instituted a flat tax—where those who earn less pay more as a proportion of their income.

Consider this: when you add up all payroll, state, federal, consumption, and local taxes, the average American worker pays 28% of their income in taxes—roughly \$20,000 per year. The rich, by contrast, pay just 20%. The situation is even worse when accounting for private health insurance costs, which push the working-class tax burden to 30% and the middle-class burden to nearly 40%. Meanwhile, for the top 1%, the effective rate drops to 28%, and for the ultra-wealthy, it sinks to just 23%. Why? Because a significant portion of the rich's income is legally exempt from taxation.

Capital Income: The Great Tax Loophole

Only 63% of total U.S. income is subject to taxation. Capital income—profits from stocks, dividends, and investments—is increasingly tax-free. Over the past 40 years, taxes on capital gains, dividends, and pension accounts have been slashed. Today, capital gains are taxed at just 20%, and most undistributed corporate profits remain entirely untaxed.

For the top 1%, half of their income comes from capital, while for multi-billionaires, it's over two-thirds. That means the wealthiest Americans enjoy a system where the majority of their income is taxed at a lower rate than the wages of working- and middle-class families.

Donald Trump's 2017 tax reform only deepened this inequality. While wages remained heavily taxed, capital income was further shielded.

The Zuckerberg Example: How the Ultra-Rich Avoid Taxes

Saez and Zucman illustrate this tax avoidance system through Mark Zuckerberg. He owns 20% of Facebook, which made \$20 billion in profit in 2018—meaning his income that year was technically \$4 billion. But since Facebook did not pay dividends, Zuckerberg's personal income wasn't taxed. Instead of distributing profits to shareholders (which would be taxable), Facebook buys back stock—a common practice among corporations to legally avoid taxation.

Even when corporate taxes are due, tax havens like Ireland allow companies to shift profits offshore, significantly reducing what they owe. Globally, corporate tax rates have plunged from an average of 49% in the 1980s to just 25% today, meaning the ultra-rich contribute even less than before.

The Heavy Tax Burden on the Poor

While the wealthy exploit tax loopholes, payroll and consumption taxes hit lower-income Americans hardest. Payroll taxes have risen from 3% to 15% since the 1980s, even as wages stagnated. Consumption taxes—like sales taxes on food and fuel—consume 10% of a poor person's income, compared to less than 1% for the rich. Meanwhile, many services used by the wealthy, such as hiring corporate lawyers or attending the opera, remain tax-free.

Historically, the U.S. counterbalanced these regressive taxes with progressive income taxes. In the aftermath of World War II, the country pioneered progressive taxation to fund public services and reduce inequality. Unlike Europe, which turned to nationalization, the U.S. used tax policy to lift all boats. But since the Reagan era, taxation has been reframed as theft, fueling an industry dedicated to tax avoidance.

The Political and Economic Consequences

The shift toward tax-free capital income isn't just about revenue—it threatens democracy. When billionaires pay less tax than working-class families, public trust in the system erodes. Why support globalization if it only enriches the ultra-wealthy? Why play by the rules when the richest openly flout them? Saez and Zucman argue that exempting capital from taxation distorts market competition, fuels monopolies, and exacerbates economic injustice.

A Path Forward: The Wealth Tax

To address this injustice, Saez and Zucman propose a bold solution: a 3% net wealth tax on billionaires. This policy is designed to tax accumulated wealth rather than just annual income.

If implemented since 1982, this tax would have reduced Bill Gates' fortune from \$97 billion to \$42 billion and Jeff Bezos' from \$160 billion to \$95 billion. Unsurprisingly, the ultra-rich oppose it.

But what's the social utility of letting billionaires amass ever-growing fortunes? Would it truly harm innovation if a billionaire's net worth were trimmed by a few dozen billion? If anything, a wealth tax could push them to reinvest in productive ventures instead of hoarding wealth and monopolizing markets. Alternatively, those billions could be redirected toward public goods, such as universal healthcare or free university education.

Saez and Zucman's book doesn't just diagnose the problem—it offers a roadmap to a fairer economic system. The question is: do we have the political will to follow it?

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